

Conservation of Momentum and a Photon-Only View in 1D Reflection-Refraction

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A classical free particle whose energy is described by $E = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) or $E = p^2/2m$ has two degenerate solutions in terms of momentum information, namely p and $-p$. These are time reversed situations of each other. In order to realize both in a problem, one requires reflection from a surface, i.e. a force and overall conservation of momentum must exist. Given that the particle energy, however, does not change, if one only considers energy as information one might argue that nothing happens when p becomes $-p$. In other words, p and $-p$ may be seen from the point of view of degenerate solutions linked to the same E in a particle-only view.

In the case of a photon reflecting and refracting, E is again one value. Thus, an incident, reflected and refracted photon may be considered different degenerate solutions in the information momentum. As argued in previous notes, given that E is the same, nothing happens if one only considers E . In terms of p , however, impulses occur. In this case, an incident photon either becomes a reflected one or a refracted one and there is a probability. This probability, however, only appears if one considers the incident, reflected and refracted photons together in one equation even though physically one has an incident photon becoming a reflected or a refracted at different times. Thus, an equation (or two because there are two unknowns) seem to be somewhat mathematical because different times are mixed which is even what happens in classical probability i.e. $1 = \text{probability}(\text{heads up}) + \text{probability}(\text{heads down})$. Physically, heads up and heads down cannot occur at the same time, but probabilities for the two can be added.

Thus, it seems that one requires an expression for probability linked to the various p values of the incident, reflected and refracted photons. It is, however, not at all clear what this probability should be. At the same time, if the photon reflects, it interacts with the n_1-n_2 index of refraction interface and receives $-2p$ momentum, while if it refracts, it receives p_2-p_1 momentum. We argue that physically such an interaction must take place within a region dx of finite size and that one cannot distinguish between p incident and p reflected $-2p$ or p refracted $+ p_2-p_1$ in this x region. Thus, we seek a function such that $F(p, x) = F(p \text{ reflected}=-p, x) F(2p, x)$ or $F(p, x) = F(p \text{ refracted}, x) F(p_2-p_1, x)$. "X" must appear because one could have either the incident momentum or the final two momenta anywhere in x and one cannot distinguish between the two. $F(p, x)$, however, defined in this way follows the product rule of an AND probability. We thus consider this as the probability required when treating 1D photon reflection-refraction from a photon-only viewpoint. In other words, we rely on momentum conservation in order to develop a probability function which is then applied to a photon only viewpoint for reflection-refraction using continuity of $F(p, x)$ in space and continuity of its first derivative. In other words, the quantum form, $\exp(ipx)$, emerges from trying to mathematically describe momentum conservation.

Degenerate Energy Solutions

Degenerate energy solution exist in the simplest case of a free particle, i.e. $E = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) or $E = p^2/2m$. In particular, one has a degenerate solution with p and another with $-p$. If one is not interested in p (momentum) information and how it physically changes, then one

focuses only on energy, then nothing happens if one reflects a photon or particle with rest mass. From the point of view of momentum, however, an impulse occurs and there must be conservation of momentum. The key point we wish to stress is that in the case of degenerate solutions with the same energy, one may focus only on the particle or photon and in a sense, ignore the reaction, in the simple p , $-p$ case, even though it exists and is linked with conservation laws.

Matters, however, become more complicated in the 1D reflection-refraction case of a photon (or a particle for that matter). In this situation, there are three degenerate solutions all with the same energy E , namely the incident photon with p , the reflected, with $-p$ and the refracted with p_2 . Here one has an $n_1=1$ versus n_2 index of refraction interface in one dimension. Physically, an incident photon either reflects or refracts, but such analysis does not allow one to consider probabilities for these events. One needs a probability expression so one may write incident, reflected and refracted terms in the same equation. If the incident photon carries a weight of 1, one requires two equations to solve for the other two unknowns, i.e. the weights of the reflected and refracted photons.

The idea of writing a probability equation linking the reflected, refracted and incident photons seems to follow mathematically from the degeneracy of these three solutions, i.e. all have the same E , but physically there is an impulse hit in the reflected and refracted cases and these are different. Furthermore, this impulse hit must conserve overall momentum. We ask: Can one somehow link this conservation of momentum to a probability function?

Conservation of Momentum and a Probability Function?

Classically, conservation of momentum exists and is applied to the incident and final products of a reaction. The reaction, however, occurs in time and space and one usually does not know its specific details. If one ignores time, one still should have the interaction occur in a finite region of space dx , albeit possibly a small one. If this is the case, then one should have a function $F(p,x)$ for the incident photon which is linked to an AND scenario for the final product and momentum in the interface, i.e.

$$F(p,x) = F(p \text{ reflected}=-p, x) F(2p,x) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad F(p,x) = F(p \text{ refracted}=p_2,x) F(p_1-p_2,x) \quad ((1b))$$

In this case, x must be part of the function $F(p,x)$ because one is comparing an incident photon and reactants momenta within x and they must match. ((1a)) and ((1b)), however, are in the form of an AND probability situation. In fact, they were constructed in this manner. Thus, $F(p,x)$ represents a kind of probability, Furthermore, a solution of ((1a)), ((1b)) is:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

The i is used so that the probability does not grow or shrink indefinitely with x . This allows for large interaction regions.

Thus, momentum conservation consideration yields a probability expression ((2)). In the 1D reflection-refraction case, however, it was suggested that because the various p solutions, p , $-p$, and p_2 are degenerate in E , they should appear in an equation which does not make use of the

interaction with the interface. In other words, the interaction of the interface provides the form $\exp(ipx)$ to ensure momentum conservation, but then one may take this probability and use it in a photon-only viewpoint.

Photon-Only Viewpoint

A photon-only viewpoint using probabilities combines probabilities for the degenerate solutions, namely the incident, reflected and refracted photons. Given that one uses probabilities, it is acceptable to combine all three in the same equation. Furthermore, since one uses $\exp(ipx)$, one may ask for continuity of these probabilities and their first derivatives at the interface point which may be taken to be $x=0$. This leads to two equations for two unknowns, namely weights for a reflected and refracted photon:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3a))$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = Cp2 \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3b))$$

Thus, setting $A=1$, one may solve for B and C . These are not probabilities in their own right because one may combine ((3a)) and ((3b)) by multiplying to obtain an equation for the probabilities, i.e.

$$AAp - pBB = CC p2 \quad ((4))$$

One may note that if $F(p,x)$ incident describes the whole probability of the incident photon in terms of momentum, but that product probabilities are used to create equivalents to $F(p,x)$ i.e. $F(\text{P}reflected, x)$ $F(2p,x)$ or $F(p \text{ refracted},x)$ $F(p1-p2,x)$. In writing ((3a)), one seeks an equivalent to $\exp(ipx)$ (multiplied by A) only at $x=0$ through continuity not momentum equivalence.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that degenerate energy solutions, namely ones with different momenta p , are linked with an impulse hit, but if one only thinks in terms of energy, then one may use a particle-only or photon-only viewpoint because in terms of energy nothing happens. In the case of 1D reflection-refraction at an $n1=1$ versus $n2$ index of refraction interface, one either has reflection OR refraction. A probability statement, even in classical probability, however, would combine all three energy degenerate solutions into one equation (or actually two) because one requires two equations for two unknowns assuming that an incident weight is known. The problem is that one does not have such a probability function.

We suggest that even though energy degeneracy suggests linking probabilities for the incident, reflected and refracted photons, physically impulse hits which conserve overall momentum occur at the $n1-n2$ interface.

We suggest that one may analyse the interaction in a region dx in a manner in which the momentum at x of the incident photon equals the momentum at x of the reflected or refracted photon plus extra momentum needed to balance momentum.. Because one does not know if

one has the incident photon or the products at a particle x in dx , one may write a probability equation, i.e. $F(p,x) = F(p \text{ reflected} = -p, x) F(2p, x)$ or $F(p,x) = F(p \text{ refracted} = p_2, x) F(-p_2 + p, x)$. This suggests $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution which does not grow or shrink indefinitely.

Thus, consideration of momentum conservation yields $\exp(ipx)$, but for degenerate E solutions one requires a photon-only viewpoint. To achieve this, one may write a continuity equation for $\exp(ipx)$ s for the incident, reflected and refracted photons at $x=0$ (n_1 - n_2 interface) and another for continuity of the first derivative in x . One may then multiply the two equations together to obtain a single probability equation.

In other words, momentum conservation leads to $\exp(ipx)$, but there may be cases (degenerate E situations) where one may be able to apply this probability to the photon (or particle only) ignoring, so to speak, the interaction.